

**A STUDY TO EVALUATE ENGLISH LANGUAGE MATERIALS OF
SINGLE NATIONAL CURRICULUM IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS OF LAHORE**

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Abstract

Education is one of the important instruments to build a prosperous nation. The government of Pakistan in the year 2020 developed the Single National Curriculum (SNC) and implemented it in schools. The purpose of this study is to find out the problems faced by English teachers in Single National Curriculum (SNC) in public schools of Lahore. The study has been taken twelve public schools of Lahore. The aim of this research is to examine the challenges faced by English schools teachers while teaching the Single National Curriculum. One of the significant reasons of this research is to know about teachers experience while teaching the Single National Curriculum. The present study used the mixed methods to prepare the report in which data has been collected. The Quantitative data is based on questionnaires that have been taken from forty English schools teachers of Lahore and compiled into SPSS. The data has been explored through descriptive analysis using percentages and statistics. The Qualitative data is used in this study are based on previous literature and sample work collected by participants. The semi structured interviews have been taken from eight public schools teachers and written narrative from six English teachers. The researcher had collected the data then analyzed through coding and thematic analysis. The findings show that English teachers are facing difficulties in implementing the Single National Curriculum in public schools. There are some learning problems in pronunciation, lack of trainings, lack of resources, teaching skills and methods. They are also facing the problems of their teaching skills without proper trainings. There is lack of resources too which make difficult for teachers to implement a Single National Curriculum properly. They are facing problems about teaching methodologies.

Keywords: pedagogical skills, methodology, resources, lack of teacher training.

The implications of Single National Curriculum (SNC)

Introduction

The meaning of Curriculum

The meaning of curriculum is defined as the organization as well as the purpose and content of the educational program. Secondly, it is a potential experiment for teaching young people and children about group ways of acting and thinking. Students have been found to develop some kind of master plan to resist what is included in the curriculum and how it is delivered. There are two basic and primary forms of curriculum in schools. One of them is clear curriculum. What ideas or plans teachers implement and what will happen when the plans are implemented; other forms are implicit or hidden curricula that emerge as unplanned additions to an explicit or definitive curriculum. An implicit curriculum can have negative consequences for students, but it can also have positive consequences.

Single National Curriculum

In education, Single National Curriculum is an important way to achieve educational objectives. It is divided in different ways. The One National Curriculum represents different ideologies of life and educational objectives, beliefs, traditions of the people. the implementation of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) in Pakistan, wider stakeholder rights were considered, particularly the right to education and the responsibility of states to uphold values and tolerance. The main foundations of curriculum are psychological foundations of curriculum, philosophical foundations of curriculum, social foundations of curriculum, and historical foundations of curriculum.

Single National Curriculum is the step and directions for the students. It is very important and beneficial for all the children. It has the benefits to having a Single curriculum for the

promotion and betterment of society. The purpose of this curriculum is to enjoy an equal and fair chance to receive a good and proper education. Students should have the equal rights for the education. The purpose of this curriculum is to get the fair and equal chance for all the students of Pakistan. This is a good chance for the poor students. In this way all students can get the equal rights because the English of high level medium schools in private sector where fee range is very high as compared to the students of public school students. All these institutions have different environments in term of curriculum.

In 2018, a political party of Pakistan “Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf” (PTI) launched an ambitious project to develop a Single system and curriculum in hopes of providing uniform education for all students across Pakistan. According to the National Curriculum Board, curriculum harmonization was done over a fixed four-year period, which is now approved to be implemented from pre-school to fifth grade.

Single National Curriculum’s Standards

“The curriculum is based on a standardized sequence of planned activities in which students master and practice practical learning skills and content”. The curriculum is a guide for the teachers about what is needed to learn and teach for every student. It has access to an educational experience. The structure and organization of the curriculum is designed to improve student teaching and learning. Curriculum includes the necessary methods, objectives, content, and assessments to support teaching and learning effectively. Curriculum objectives are based on learning and teaching standards or expectations. Objectives are articulated in the form of skill sets and scopes. Objectives include the student’s learning is expected.

Methods are teaching styles, decisions, procedures and the methods teachers use to engage all students in quality and meaningful learning. They facilitate the learning process with

the aim of improving and advancing the student's skills to apply and understand the material.

Methods are necessary according to the interest of student needs and learning environment.

Methods are necessary on assessment of student progress toward achieving goals.

Materials are tools for implementing methods and achieving curriculum objectives.

Materials are selected specifically for student learning. However, a number of criticisms from academic have highlighted the challenges for fundamental rights that the One National Curriculum (SNC) faces. Consequently, the Single National Curriculum's implementation should consider the rights of minorities, the culture's protection, language and the obligations of States to promote values based on international obligations of peaceful tolerance abroad and to provide access to education at home. The researcher will take a closer look at efforts to introduce a single national curriculum in Pakistan and the possible implications for teachers in public schools in Lahore.

Importance of Single National Curriculum

It has been proven that our educational program plays a vital role in nation building. Curriculum is a long-standing desire of the society. The development of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) for Pre-School Grades 1-5 is the realization of one curriculum, one nation's dream. The education system in our country caters to the educational needs of children from different walks of life. These include the private sector and the public sector. In addition, there are madrassas (religious schools in Pakistan) across the country that caters to the need of education of 2 to 3 million children. One National Curriculum is an important step for the building a strong and successful nation. To implement the one National Curriculum (SNC) in good spirit and training courses for teachers, textbooks model and an evaluation system are being

developed that will ensure delivery of education that matches and surpasses children's performance.

There is the development of Single National Curriculum in 2020 and implementation was in primary schools for the year 2020-2021, has been released by the Government of Pakistan. The focus of the study is on teachers' expectations regarding Single National Curriculum (SNC) implementation at the primary level. This study is conducted using a mixed methods strategy combining qualitative and quantitative research. Teachers are interviewed face-to-face unstructured questions. Interviews are recorded using a Smartphone call recording application. An excel spreadsheet containing the transcribed data is examined through thematic analysis.

This is the belief of teachers that the SNC will ultimately help Pakistan become a more united and powerful country. It also upholds the values of Quaid-e-Azam (Father of the Nation) and Allama Iqbal (Dreamer of Pakistan as an independent country) while ensuring equal access to high-quality education for all children. It also reduces poverty in Pakistan, but only temporarily. A fair system benefits the educator. This reduces educational disparities and strengthens national cohesion. According to the data, teachers in all education systems are most concerned about the SNC implementation, obstacles to “freedom of choice of students in education”, lack of resources, incompetence of teachers and resistance from stakeholders and teachers are through print and online media, more attention should be given to SNC. Based on the findings is that the refresher courses for in-service teachers are recommended and more funds need to be allocated to address the lack of resources in schools that hinder the performance of SNC. Loan programs must also be introduced for private sector schools which cannot implement SNC due to lack of resources.

Vision for the Assessment of English Curriculum

English is always been considered an important and good skill in education at all levels and the level of international communication and for individual development for a better future. English is an important medium for the students to talk or communicate effectively with other people both in writing and orally. Learning a second language provides students the opportunities of social, cultural, intellectual, emotional and material knowledge that is useful for building a multicultural society. The Single National Curriculum 2006 has been revised at various stages due to the changing demand at global and local levels. A first review is conducted at the Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT) level in 2017 to update the ICT curriculum for schools. In 2019, the government's current vision is to develop the one curriculum for all education sectors in the country. As a result, there are two areas for improvement found i.e. procedures of assessment and teaching processes. English Teachers should provide the necessary skills to complement the textbooks and other resources and should pay special attention to the skills, i.e., speaking, reading, writing and listening to the students. It is believed that these essential goals outlined in the Single National Curriculum fill this gap.

Literature Review

The goals of Single National Curriculum

Curriculum is finding as the main and important method for achieving educational goals in education. It is divided in many different ways. Single National Curriculum represents a different way of life, such as the educational goals, beliefs and traditions of a nation. For the implementation of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) in Pakistan, the broader rights of stakeholders are respected and considered, particularly the right to education and the responsibility of states to uphold values and tolerance.

The current interim government of Pakistan and previous governments have also started to rebuild the education system of Pakistan to put the country on the right track. Government policy makers have rightly said that Pakistan's hospital education system is the root of all social and economic problems. The Government of Pakistan has launched National Curriculum (SNC) to support the education system which will be implemented across the country. All existing levels of education in Pakistan will follow a Single curriculum and it is implemented and people from all socio-economic backgrounds will be able to receive a Single education. Madrasahs (religious schools in Pakistan) will be built into the new education system. Madrasahs will teach all modern trends, and students will take school board exams. Federal Department of Education and Training, 2020), about 35,000 madrasahs will become schools.

Curriculum Development in Pakistan

Pakistan came into being in 1947. At that time the base of education was not very strong and unable to build a diverse structure and good reliable education system in the country. For this, at that time it necessary not only to expand the education system but also to bring the entire education system in line with the needs of cultural, social and economic of the country. In 1947,

the Pakistan Educational Conference was held to monitor the education system. The conference proposes to bring the curriculum according to the ideals and requirements of the country and encourage the integration of various components of education. “Teaching support and teacher training are found as an important part to improve teacher performance” (Freeman, Simonsen, Briere&Macsua-Gage.2014).

Education is the light that spreads far and wide, and the teacher is the source and source of that light. Therefore, it is a very important and necessary part for the performance and training of teachers in the field of education is the role and contribution of teacher development is one of the best requirements for the promotion and improvement of education. The government plans to introduce the Single National Curriculum (ENC) in primary schools in 2021 to 2022. Firstly the focus is on teaching English as a language skill, which is content from the One National Curriculum.

English is the language of the institution because it is associated with technology which focuses on globalization and economic development and country modernization (Tsui and Tollefson, 2006). The pressures of external and internal determined the position of the English language in the fields of educational, political and economic which changed the role of the English language in indirect and direct language. Rahman (2009) believes that globalization is increasing or developing with the power of English language in Pakistan because English leads to more and better opportunities and employment.

The demand for English as the language of instruction in colleges, universities and schools at the expense of local languages are increasing. It is an important and compulsory subject in the curriculum of Pakistan institutes and institutions. “For this reason the aim of

English language teachers is to equip students with critical awareness and literacy knowledge” (Kress, 2003).

In Pakistan, English plays an important role in the education, socially, economically and politically life of the country (Mansoor, 2005). Pakistan is a developing country has been facing many challenges since its inception. An important problem is the education system of Pakistan, as we know that after the British colonialism in the Indian subcontinent. In Pakistan education system is divided into different educational media. There are high schools of English, high schools of Urdu and religious madrassas that have created disparity between students and the country's residents.

Curriculum introduced to raise the standard of education in Pakistan and It reform is a dynamic and continuous process that needs to be updated to meet the growing needs of the world. It is the primary source of learning for teachers and students. Tyler (1957), Caswell and Campbell (1935) and Ragan (1960) defined curriculum as a planned activity that a student carries out under the control of a school. The Single National curriculum is based on the basic goals and objectives of the nation and can be achieved only by following the national curriculum.

In Pakistan the improvement of curriculum is started with a report in 1959 but through the National Education Policies of 1998, the problem remained persistent and uncontrollable. In 2006 “public schools were reformed the low cost private schools and provinces were given the right to reject or accept revisions” (Jamil, 2009).

Since 2006, the Single National Curriculum has been one of the reforms in education by recent governments in Pakistan. This aim of restructuring the national curriculum is to introduce a uniform system of education across the country and to address social disparities. The aims of Single national curriculum are to bring about responsible citizenship, tolerance, conflict

management and engagement with all institutions in Pakistan through content, assessment methodology and learning tools.

Significance of Education in Single National Curriculum

Education is an important tool for analytical cost and capital accumulation for ultimate socio-economic development. It plays an important role in the cultivation, preservation and transmission of cultural heritage from one generation to another. Education is the awareness and knowledge of how to make the most of one's abilities, enabling the individual to make informed and thoughtful decisions and choices. "It increases the skill of people and creates skilled labor that leads the economy towards development" (Farah, Fauzee&Daud, 2014).

Education is the process of bringing about beneficial changes in the attitudes and behavior of people. It facilitates acquisition and learning of knowledge, beliefs, habits, values, skills and nature. These procedures for making appropriate changes and acquiring knowledge are the analytical goals of education and are usually achieved through the curriculum, taking into account all other aspects of its implementation in the classroom. "It is of great significance for an individual as well as for the society, economically, socially and morally"(Hussein and vostanis, 2013).

According to the Ministry of Vocational Training and Federal Education, "the aims and objectives of the "One National Curriculum" are ensure that all the children in Pakistan have equal rights to high quality education and social mobility" (Ministry of Federal Education and Training) (2020). As a result the national unity will be ensured. In Pakistan tolerance for diversity is achieved by teaching students respect for different religions and cultures. Emphasis will be placed on teaching creative and critical thinking rather than rote culture. Students will be taught Communication Technologies (ICT) and Information. Curriculum quality will ensure that

everyone has equal rights. In short, “the government of Pakistan has started to make ambitious goals to eliminate Pakistan's class society which in the long run will eliminate the threat of economic inequality” (Shaikh, 2020).

Teachers use many metaphors to describe their work. There are many roles for teachers such as teacher, controller, administrator, evaluator, prompter, participant, resource, tutor, observer etc. “the development of society is the teacher who make the learners to find the world around them and investigate the stock of knowledge” (Banner and Prenzel, 2012).

Standards of Education in Single National Curriculum

The term standards in education has included in all kinds of policies. However, its definition is unclear due to the involvement of a large number of stakeholders and the complex nature of the teaching-learning process. Educational standards are defined as “a set of components that constitute the process and outcome of an education system”. The term quality education has also been defined in two ways “Input or output”. The quality of education is related to the resources of the school, such as teacher qualifications, teaching, teaching and learning materials, curriculum, resources and facilities (academic, physical, financial, and others) needed to sustain the school. Thus, the instruction level corresponds to the input data. If the input is of the quality of acceptable, the output will also be of excellent quality (Mulenga, 2020).

Thus, the educational quality corresponds to the input data. If the input is of acceptable quality, the output will also be of excellent quality. Educational impact and curriculum as input are related to each other. The curriculum design and nature determines the learning process to achieve the desired standards and outcomes. Quality is central to education and includes the characteristics of desired processes, learners, facilities, materials, learning materials, leadership, management, and learning outcomes. The Quality of education is that meets basic learning

needs and improves students' lives and overall life experiences. "Education of the teacher means knowledge and skills of subject and the skills to impart the knowledge and develop skills in students" (Darling-Hammond, 2012).

The 2009 National Education Policy recognizes six pillars of quality, including curriculum, system of assessment, textbooks, and teachers, environment of learning and relevance of education to practical life. These pillars of curriculum is the most important and fundamental pillar in which all learning and teaching activities take place. Therefore it is very important part of the curriculum is that it takes into account all the requirements for basic and effective learning. The standards are used as a reference site to assess the quality of the inputs, outputs and processes of the education system. Kelly-Gangi&Patterson said that Education is the filling of the pail and lightning of fire.

In education standards are used to evaluate the quality of education and student achievement. Standards and specifications are important for the inputs, outputs and processes of an education system. Standards define "what students need to know and be able to do at a particular level of education". The standards also define "the skills and knowledge that a student should possess at critical moments in their academic career". Standards are used as a site of reference for evaluating the quality of input, output and process of the education system. The standards also have as a basis for improving education across the country and enable student achievement to be assessed and measured in terms of outcomes.

It is also important for those involved in evaluation, analysis, feedback and research. Therefore, there are needed as a national resource to define the skills, knowledge and position that students should possess at all stages of education at the primary, secondary and upper

secondary levels to give a consistent foundation. And obviously young children can be prepared to be their best Future education and professional careers in the world.

Deficiency of development and Training

The institutions of education do not spend some available funds for the development of teachers and training. They do not want to send to organize and conduct workshops, seminars, courses and conferences to develop themselves and learn modern and contemporary methodologies and teaching methods. Few teachers are selected for training, and most teachers are not given the opportunity to improve their teaching skills. It is an important and essential for quality work that Teaching is hard work. There is a lack of training opportunities for teachers in Pakistan. There are many educational institutions in the country and these institutions are either under-resourced or poorly managed due to lack of funds and trained personnel like the trainers and administrators. “Several studies showing that the most significant school-based factor is the quality of teacher’s achievement of students” (Mincu, 2015).

There are no real libraries where students can study and read books. Books are extinct and unavailable. There are no modern electronic libraries in the library; especially government schools do not have computer equipment. Neither adequate lighting nor generators can make learning comfortable for ambitious and motivated students in case of load and power outages. The Overcrowded classrooms, corridors full of students, inadequate teachers, laboratories without the necessary equipment for practical teaching and learning lead to low quality and hopelessness of education (Louis, 1987).

Low budgetary allotment for education

The system of education in Pakistan has been paralyzed due to allocation of funds and resources in the budget. The budget of education which is certainly not enough to meet the

growing needs of the population, inclusion of modern and advanced technology in the education system and high taxes, low wages are also obstacles to the expansion of this sector. Hourly fees for visiting teachers are also taxed at the expense of 10 percent of applicants and 20 percent of non-applicants, which is truly unfair and reduces the limited revenue.

In many countries such as Sri Lanka and Bangladesh the share of education in the total budget of the country is increasing but in Pakistan it is steadily decreasing (Sian, 2012).

Investigation of the results of Single National Curriculum

An important and prominent benefit of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) is the promotion of equality of social. When it is fully implemented, all children have the fair and equal opportunity to receive and get a good education (Robert, 2020). There is unity at every level which will lead to national unity. Disparities between social class and inequality will be reduced creating fairer opportunities of social mobility for all.

As two schools are the same, one of the main and important disadvantages of a fixed curriculum is the lack of flexibility. It is overly reactive and prescriptive as a barrier to change. This Single national curriculum is limiting the revolution in curriculum design. These two of the previous shortcomings can affect autonomy of teacher and resulting in less professional independence and insight. However the government has identified only outline of chapters to be included in the syllabus if schools agree they need to build more, they can do so.

Methodology

Population of the Study

This study is considered a group for a study or statistical reasoning. The target population of the study is twelve Public sectors. The written Narratives have been filled from six female teachers at public schools of Lahore. The questionnaires have been filled from forty female teachers at public schools of Lahore. This research is based on probability sampling as the subjects of population are selected randomly for achieving the objective of research. Open ended and semi structured interviews have been taken from eight teachers of public schools. The purpose of choosing government school teachers is to know about their difficulties while teaching English of Single National Curriculum. They are facing the difficulties in teaching and implications in teaching the Single National Curriculum.

Research Instruments

Three tools are used to conduct the study to get the results in better way.

1. Quantitative data has been collected through the questionnaires of close ended from the forty teachers of public schools of Lahore.
2. Qualitative data is based on semi structured open ended interviews and probes that have been taken from the eight teachers of public schools of Lahore.
3. Written narrative has been taken from six teachers to know about teacher's experiences of teaching while teaching English the Single National Curriculum (SNC).

The collection of data is based on questionnaire which is close ended from the teachers at public schools of Lahore. Then the data has been collected through interviews unstructured, open ended protocol from the teachers of public schools. Written narrative is used to know about teachers experiences of teaching about Single National Curriculum (SNC). The following two

categories of research methodology exist; Qualitative and Quantitative. In qualitative research, information is acquired through conversational techniques, open ended questions and face to face interaction. The collection of responses is not numerical.

Aims and Objectives

1. To evaluate the impacts of Single National Curriculum (SNC) teacher's perspective of public schools of Lahore through structured interviews of teachers.
2. To identify the challenges confronting by public school teachers of Lahore while teaching English of Single National Curriculum (SNC) through unstructured interviews.
3. To discover experiences of teachers in written narrative of Single National Curriculum (SNC) at primary level of public schools of Lahore.

Research questions

- Q1.** What are the views of the public-school teachers of Lahore on the Single National Curriculum (SNC)?
- Q2.** What type of problems public school teachers faced while teaching English of the Single National Curriculum (SNC)?
- Q3.** What would be the experiences of teachers regarding teaching the Single National Curriculum (SNC) at the primary level in public schools in Lahore?

Justification of study

The aim of this research is to examine the impact of Single National Curriculum in government schools of Lahore. There are semi-structured protocols interviews, questionnaires and written narratives of teachers of public schools in Lahore. The aim of this study is to provide teachers' perspectives on the Single National Curriculum (SNC). One of the significant reasons of this research is to learn about teacher experience while teaching the Single National Curriculum. Do English teachers have the teaching skills and methodology? Is there lack of teaching skills in government schools in Lahore? What are the implications coming for teachers in teaching English?

Statement of Problem

The public-school teachers are facing challenges in implementing the Single National Curriculum (SNC) in classroom skills of teaching, lesson planning, teaching methods, lack of resources and some barriers of teaching in public schools of Lahore. Lack of teaching skills and teacher training are major problems for teachers. The focus of this study is to know about the implications of the public school teachers about Single National Curriculum.

The primary role of teacher is to teach and support the students in learning and general understanding of the English material. Pakistan is facing some major challenges in terms of educational programs. The main challenge is the development of teacher training. Training institutions for teachers are also facing financial difficulties. There are shortage of funds, teaching aids and text materials and other some related resources in educational institutions. This research shows that teacher education programs are facing significant challenges in terms of quality, lack of resources and policy. One of the most important problems identified by the study is the lack of training of public school teachers. Teachers have no clear idea about how to plan

lessons to teach the Single National Curriculum. The term teaching methods refers to the general principles, teaching and management strategies using in classroom learning.

This study is designed to explore the impact of Single National Curriculum of public schools of Lahore. Teachers have awareness of teaching methods but they are not properly trained about it and how to apply these methods in the classroom. Teachers are facing difficulties in teaching English because they are not trained. There is also lack of resources in government schools. The purpose of this study is to find out the problems of teachers.

Findings of Quantitative Data

This part of the chapter analyzes and discusses quantitative data. All data containing participants' responses is carefully coded and compiled into SPSS. The data has been explored through descriptive analysis using percentages and statistics. The research of quantitative is an organized method of collecting information and examining it for decision making. This data is related to numbers.

By having more information to study, more accurate results can be obtained by having in depth information of the study. Closed queries are used in this research method because researchers usually want to collect statistical data. There are various tools that are used in quantitative methods to collect the data.

On Table one, Respondents who answered questions 1 to 6 are feeling encouraging and motivating because they have the skills and new methods. Teaching is very important for the teaching of the National Curriculum. The questions about skills and teaching methods were highly motivated from respondents. However the highest percentage makes evident the most rampant value out of the 40 respondents. 70% strongly agree, 20% agree, 7% moderately agree and 3% disagree on the importance of skills and teaching methods. According to these results, teaching skills and new methods are very important for the teaching of the Single National Curriculum. Skills play an important role in learning SNC. It is very useful for teaching both teachers and students.

On Table 2, respondents who answered questions seven to twelve also showed enthusiasm and great help in having the resources to teach the CNC. These responses show that resources play an important role in teaching the CNC. It is more useful for teaching curriculum and easy to understand for students. However, the highest percentage makes clear the most rampant meaning: 50% strongly agree, 30% agree, 15% disagree, and 5% strongly disagree. So, 80% of the answers show that the resources are useful for learning and make things simpler and more conceptual. The government should provide resources to help teachers and students. Public schools lack resources.

On Table three, respondents answering questions thirteen to twenty show that teacher training is also very important for teachers. The One National Curriculum is easier to teach to public school teachers after training. However, the highest percentage makes evident the most rampant value of the 70% who fully agree that teacher training for public school teachers is very necessary. 20% agree and 10% disagree. Teaching is an important part for English teachers. According to these responses, this shows that learning is beneficial for teachers and makes teaching easier. This is very helpful for both teachers and students. The government must take steps to overcome barriers to improve student achievement in public schools. They must train public school teachers at least once a month. According to these responses, the CNC is not easy, especially for older, untrained teachers. This shows that learning is very important and improves the knowledge of public-school teachers.

Finding the Qualitative data

The qualitative data is used in this study are based on previous literature and sample work collected by participants. The researcher has been collected the data from interviews and written narrative then used coding to analyze the narrative and interview data. Quality research is a process associated with an inquiry. The findings of qualitative data will helps to create a complete understanding of issues or problems in their natural language. Qualitative research is a non-statistical method.

Qualitative research largely depends on the experience of the researchers and the questions used to study the sample. The sample size is limited to eight female teachers. Questions are open ended asked in such a way that another question or set of questions arises. The written narrative has been taken from six teachers. The purpose of all collecting data from protocol is to collect information from a sample.

Thematic analysis of Study

Theme	Sub-Theme	Descriptive Codes
Teachers are facing problems to teach SNC	Lack of trainings	Teachers understand the concept of English SNC but feel difficult to deliver in a large class.
		Teachers have knowledge but find it difficult to deliver in class.
	Lack of new Methodology	They feel difficulties to teach absent students.
		Students don't take interest learn or listen the teachers.
	Lack of Management	There is a shortage of teachers. It creates a hurdle for teachers to manage two classes together.
		Students face difficulties listening to the teacher in this way.
	Lake of Resources	Teachers feel difficulties to speak English with students.
		They are unable to deliver lecture in English and found difficult to make them understand.
		There are no resources that make the lecture understand in better way.
		Teachers have no funds or resources that can be used for students.

Encoding is a qualitative data analysis strategy in which some characteristics of the data are given a meaningful label that allows the researcher to recognize the relevant content that encompasses the data. It is the process of organizing and labeling the qualitative data to bring out the various relationships and themes between them. The researcher is used coding to analyze all qualitative data. According to the research, coding shows that teaching skills are necessary and are very important for teaching any subject. If teachers have proper English language skills and methods, it is easy to understand and make students understand correctly.

Conclusion

To conclude the research, researcher agrees on this point that in education progress is almost impossible without action in education. The growth and development of education, the support provided by teachers are directly related to all socio-economic development and progress. The youth and good-hearted minds of a community or country are shaped, guided and transformed by teachers because teacher plays an important role in the education of every child life. A good teacher may have all the things which are helpful for the student's future. There must be trainings from government for the teachers. It is useful for the future of students that they learn new things from up-to-date resources. Resources are useful for increasing of knowledge in their life. It helped to improve their knowledge and from new methodologies they will clear their concepts and knowledge in better way. In Islam, the duties of the teacher are better defined and he or she is given significant responsibility for the growth of their charges. This great value placed on teachers calls for improved teacher education especially teacher training, which is an essential component of teacher education. There are a number of serious problems with teacher training such as finding qualified teaching candidates, providing them with the necessary and correct skills, lack of resources in pedagogical institutions, teachers

discouraged from doing their job well, uneven distribution of qualified and effective teachers, dual education system, etc. etc. However practical measures such as spending money, rooting out corruption, and supporting institutions can help modernize teacher training in Pakistan. Despite a thorough evaluation of the literature, a weak point of the study is the reference to the difficulties of teacher training in general. The research suggests that there is a need for training in areas that are specific to the subject. In addition, a deeper understanding of the subject requires a thorough systematic study of the literature and empirical research. To conclude the all, it is found that the teachers should have the facilities for the proper teaching of English in public schools. Teachers have no proper trainings and facilities from government. In this way they are facing the problems to teach the students of public school students. The teachers must be trained regularly; only then other changes can come into education system and can really impact students positively.

Future recommendations

The following recommendations were put forward as one of the reasons for the results of this study:

- 1.** Before and after the introduction of SNC, refresher courses should be offered to improve the skills of teachers so that teachers can cope with the difficulties they will face and overcome their resistance to SNC.
- 2.** Print and electronic media should be used to spread the word about the importance of SNC.
- 3.** More funds need to be allocated to address the lack of resources in schools so that SNC can be effectively implemented.
- 4.** Teachers and students should be rewarded and recognized for their efforts to help develop a sense of camaraderie and enthusiasm for SNA implementation at the primary school level.

5. According to this recommendation, SNC should be fully implemented in all education systems to ensure quality education.

6. Additional actions need to be taken to address Education for All issues, such as providing financial assistance to students from low-income families in the form of scholarships and recognizing and rewarding students with exceptional abilities.

The system of education and teacher training is facing many difficulties and challenges in Pakistan. There is always room for improvement. A democratic community and a society and a society where human development and education are highly valued teacher education and issues related to the quality of teachers are always a priority. (Cochran-Smith and Zeichner) Since Pakistan is on the path to democracy serious efforts and effort should be made in regard to teacher education. When teacher get the teachers trainings it give the opportunities for professional development to learn new things, methods and the ways, strategies, skills etc. when teacher get skills the automatically feel confident and motivated and happy to attain best things for their students. If the teacher will be happy and confident students automatically fell comfortable with their teachers and studies. Teachers training programs not only impact teachers but students too. Only a one teacher who is fully skilled can go on impact many or thousand students. He or She has a big role to play in nation building because students are the citizens of tomorrow.

The discovery and results of the study indicated that teacher training issues could be addressed by securing government ownership and building trust and accountability in school systems, minimizing political interference, and respecting merit in teacher recruitment and provision Facilities for teachers and teacher training in Pakistan.

References

- Abdul, P. D. (n.d.). Retrieved from Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies: <https://publishing.globalcsrc.org/jbsee/>
- Adeel Abbas, D. I. (2022, June 21). *SINGLE NATIONAL CURRICULUM AT SCHOOL LEVEL IN PAKISTAN: EXPECTED CHALLENGES, MERITS AND DEMERITS*. Retrieved from Palarch: <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/11167>
- Ahmad, I. (2014, June). *Critical Analysis of the Problems of Education in Pakistan: Possible Solutions*. Retrieved from Researchgate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287580318_Critical_Analysis_of_the_Problems_of_Education_in_Pakistan_Possible_Solutions
- Alkhaldi, A. A. (n.d.). *Developing a Principled Framework for Materials Evaluation: Some Considerations*. Retrieved from Journal: <https://journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/alls/article/view/39>
- Chaudhary, N. U. (n.d.). *Implications of Single Curriculum*. Retrieved from Learnpak: <http://learnpak.com.pk/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Implications-of-Single-Curriculum-Nida-Usman-Ch.pdf>
- Hanif, N. (2020, September 12). *SNC and the language question*. Retrieved from The News International: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/713502-snc-and-the-language-question>
- Kabir, S. M. (2016, July). *METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION*. Retrieved from Researchgate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325846997_METHODS_OF_DATA_COLLECTION

- Kamran Akhtar Siddiqui, D. S. (n.d.). *Teacher Training in Pakistan: Overview of Challenges and their Suggested Solutions*. Retrieved from Researchgate:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350515685_Teacher_Training_in_Pakistan_Overview_of_Challenges_and_their_Suggested_Solutions
- Kamran Akhtar Siddiqui, S. H. (2021, March). *Teacher Training in Pakistan: Overview of Challenges and their Suggested Solutions*. Retrieved from Journal:
<https://www.journal.ia-education.com/index.php/ijorer/article/view/91>
- Masood Ahmed Dool. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://journal.ia-education.com/index.php/ijorer/article/view/91>
- Mertens, D. M. (2012, October 3). *What Comes First? The Paradigm or the Approach?*
Retrieved from SAGE: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1558689812461574>
- Muhammad Afzal Javed, A. A. (2017, March). *Educational Development in Pakistan: A Critical Appraisal of Muhammad Pervez Musharraf Presidency (1999-2008)*. Retrieved from International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications:
<https://www.ijsrp.org/research-paper-0317.php?rp=P636273>
- Muhammad Jahanzaib, G. F. (n.d.). *Review of Single National Curriculum with Perspective of the Education of Children with Visual Impairment at Primary Level in Punjab Pakistan*. Retrieved from Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies:
<https://publishing.globalcsrc.org/ojs/index.php/jbsee/article/view/1836>
- Muhammad Shokat Zaman 1, K. S. (n.d.). *Implementation of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) at Primary Level: Teachers' Expectations and Concerns*. Retrieved from Jahan-e-Tahqeeq: <https://jahan-e-tahqeeq.com/index.php/jahan-e-tahqeeq/article/view/507>

NATIONAL CURRICULUM FRAMEWORK. (n.d.). Retrieved from

<http://www.mofept.gov.pk/PolicyDetail/NDdkODg1YzctNmVhZS00YWU1LWEzMTMtMDdiNDM1YTbkNzk4>

Saba Iqbal, D. I. (2022). *Teacher's Perceptions About Single National Curriculum: An Enquiry of Primary School Teachers in Lahore*. Retrieved from Webology:

<https://www.webology.org/abstract.php?id=2954>

Shaukat, D. S. (2021, September 4). *Challenges of the Single National Curriculum*. Retrieved from Pakistan Today: <https://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2021/09/24/challenges-of-the-single-national-curriculum/>

Yubaedi Siron, R. M. (2017, November). *Proceedings of the International Conference on Diversity and Disability Inclusion in Muslim Societies (ICDDIMS 2017)*. Retrieved from Atlantis Press: <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/icddims-17/25893016>

Zaman, M. S. (2021). *Implementation of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) at Primary Level: Teachers' Expectations and Concerns*. Retrieved from Jahan-e-Tahqeeq: <http://jahan-e-tahqeeq.com/index.php/jahan-e-tahqeeq/article/view/507>